

SMART COMPOSITES APPLIED TO CONTINUOUS IN-SERVICE DAMAGE MONITORING OF GLASS/POLYMER INDUSTRIAL PARTS

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SUMMARY: This paper aims to develop a monitoring method making it possible to control the damage of glass/resin materials in-service in order to prevent any catastrophic failure (preventive maintenance). Carbon fibre resistive sensors are introduced directly inside the composite materials during manufacturing. The increase of their electric resistance, caused by the elongation and then the rupture of carbon filaments during loading of the composite structure, is monitored. Finally the electric response of the sensors is modelled in order to develop a real time damage monitoring system. Statistic functions such as Weibull or sigmoid functions are implemented to describe the successive failure phenomenon of the carbon filaments. The concept is validated on a composite pipe subjected to biaxial loading.

KEYWORDS: smart materials, damage monitoring, carbon fibre, glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP), dynamic fatigue, failure, composite structures, tubes

BACKGROUND

Health monitoring of composite materials has been carried out until now by non destructive testing methods, such as X ray, acoustic emissions, ultrasonic inspection... Nevertheless, these techniques show several drawbacks such as high monetary investments, difficulty to use the testing appliances on site in good conditions and necessity of long inactivity periods for the equipment to be controlled. For the last ten years research programs have been carried out in order to solve these problems by a direct location of some sensors inside composite materials during their manufacture (most of the time optic fibres and piezoelectric sensors) [1-4] or by using their conductive reinforcement fibres as resistive sensors [5-7]. These new materials which are able to continuously control some of their properties are called smart composites. In the present work, a different approach has been chosen. The aim is to develop a smart glass/resin composite being able to follow the in-service damage of industrial parts for a purpose of preventive maintenance. The damage sensor used is a carbon tow. The increase of its electric resistance, caused by the elongation and then the rupture of the carbon fibres during loading of the composite structure, is monitored.

A basic study [8,9] has been first carried out on test coupons in order to check the feasibility of the damage monitoring method, to calibrate the sensors and to investigate the possible parameters of influence: physical characteristics of the tows (nominal elongation at break, number of filaments), structure of the host composite material, loading mode (monotonic tension, bending or shear, repeated progressive tension, dynamic bending fatigue), environmental conditions (temperature and moisture). The different ways to process the sensor responses have also been discussed.

The results obtained have shown that carbon tows can be used as resistive damage integrated sensors providing their characteristics are adapted to the critical strains of the structure to be monitored. It is important to point out that a calibration stage is necessary in order to effectively use this technology and that the application field is restricted to non conductive composites. Among the potential parameters of influence investigated, the carbon fibre elongation at break and linear density appear to be of prime importance. The moisture content of the environment has no effect on the sensor response and the small effect of the temperature can easily be taken into account through a correction factor. Regarding the processing of the sensor responses, it is possible to use the electric resistance increase caused either by the fracture of the conductive carbon fibres which provides partially non reversible information, or by the fibre elongation which provides a reversible response with a much lower amplitude. From a practical point of view, prior to the integration of the sensor in a composite structure, it is necessary to determine both the stress map (location and direction) and the governing laws of the material. The sensor integration is then possible after having chosen the characteristics of the carbon tows in order to obtain an easily measurable and reproducible response for the level of stress considered as being critical for the part to be monitored.

The aim of the present paper is now to validate this monitoring concept on industrial parts under complex loading and to develop a mathematical model for the sensor response. In a first part, different sensors are calibrated in monotonic tension. Then the damage monitoring method is applied on composite pipes under increasing and dynamic internal pressure with end effects (biaxial loading). Finally statistic functions such as Weibull or sigmoid functions are implemented to describe the electric response of the resistive carbon fibre sensors.

EXPERIMENTAL MEANS

Standard tensile test specimens with end tabs were made by contact moulding of a E-glass (0/90°) non woven fabric and a vinylester (Derakane 411-45) matrix with a fibre content of 46 % by weight. Four types of carbon tows are used as resistive sensors; their references are given in table 1. The industrial composite parts chosen here are E-glass/epoxy filament wound pipes of 100 mm diameter and $\pm 55^\circ$ winding angle, manufactured by Wavin Repox. In that case, the sensors are located on the pipe outer surface and embedded in an epoxy resin: the final practice would be of course to integrate the carbon fibre sensor inside the pipe wall during manufacturing, in the same way as for test coupons.

Tensile tests were performed on a ZWICK 1474 machine, equipped with an extensometer, at a cross-head rate of 1 mm/min. The measurement of the electric resistance of the carbon tows occurs by means of either a current divider bridge [8] or a micro ohm meter (HP 34420A) if a higher accuracy is required. Acoustic emissions have also been monitored by means of a

LOCAN AT acquisition unit from PAC. Tests on pipes under increasing or dynamic internal water pressure with end effects were carried out on an hydraulic testing unit at a rate of 20 bar/min for monotonic tests and at a frequency of 25 cycles/min for dynamic tests.

Table 1. References and properties of the carbon tows

Fibre reference	Elongation at break (%)	Number of filaments
TORAYCA® T700 SC (HR)	2,1	12000
Carbone HR-3K	1,5 à 1,7	3000
TORAYCA® M 40 (HM)	0,6	1000, 3000, 6000, 12000
DIALEAD® K13A10 (THM)	0,36	10000

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Calibration of the sensors in monotonic tension on test coupons

Figure 1 shows the results obtained during a monotonic tensile test (parallel to the carbon fibre direction) on test specimens containing carbon tows of 2,1%, 1.5/1.7%, 0,6% and 0,36% nominal ultimate elongation respectively. The relative electric resistance versus strain curves for the four different carbon tows and the mean stress-strain curve have been plotted. The electric resistance of the sensor increases with specimen elongation: at first slightly only and almost linearly due to the carbon fibre elongation, which practically is not visible for certain carbon tow types; then more rapidly after a certain strain level, which varies according to the carbon tow type. The change of slope of the electric resistance vs. strain curves is caused by the first fractures of the conductive carbon fibres and constitutes a specific signal of the sensor which can be easily detected. It appears logically that, the higher the ultimate elongation of the carbon tow, the higher the strain for which the change of slope of the electric resistance curve appears. The end of linearity of the stress-strain curve (knee point) corresponds to the end of the elastic behaviour and can be associated to the beginning of the global non recoverable damage of the material.

Fig.1: Electric responses for different carbon fibre tows (0,36%, 0,6%, 1,5/1,7% and 2,1% nominal elongation at break) (tensile test on test coupons)

For carbon tows of 0,36 % and 0,6 % ultimate elongations, the change of slope of the electric resistance vs. strain curves occurs before the end of the elastic behaviour, and thus, before the first critical damage of the host composite: that means that both carbon tows are sensitive enough and suit well to act as preventive damage sensors for this particular host composite

structure.

Application to pipes under internal pressure

$\Delta R/\epsilon$ curves corresponding to the different carbon fibre tows for a given loading mode are available from the previous tests on standard specimens. Now in order to instrument a part in such a way that a significant electric response of the sensor occurs at the onset of the first critical damage of the host composite structure, it is necessary to know as a preliminary the critical strain level of the part to be monitored. In our case, the first damage of the pipes subjected to an internal pressure with end effects occurs at 0,16% axial strain and 0,54% hoop strain (knee-point on stress-strain curves). As a consequence the best choice is to instrument the pipe with a carbon tow of 0,36% nominal ultimate elongation located in the hoop direction (its electric response due to filaments fractures occurs at 0,45% elongation on the basis of tensile tests on test coupons).

The short-term stress-axial & hoop strains curves are reported on figure 2, as well as the variation of the electric resistance of the hoop located carbon tow. The sudden increase of the electric resistance due to carbon fibres fracture occurs at 0,50% elongation, that is to say at a pressure level just preceding the material first damage. Indeed the sensor effectively acts as a preventive damage sensor for the instrumented composite part. Moreover it reacts well before weeping (loss of watertightness of the pipe wall), which occurs at 1,05% hoop strain: This allows the user to intervene before the final failure of the part. The reproducibility of the results, checked on three pipes, appears to be good (scattering less than 5%).

Fig.2: Composite pipe under increasing internal pressure - Response of a carbon fibre sensor (0,36% nominal elongation at break, 10K linear density) located in the hoop direction

Then, in order to simulate an intensive use of the pipe at long term under a loading level near the critical damage point of the structure, dynamic fatigue tests at constant amplitude of stress are carried out, the upper pressure limit (115 MPa) being 20% less than the knee-point of the stress-strain curves recorded under increasing internal pressure. Figure 3 shows, as a function of the cycle number, the maximum and minimum electric resistances corresponding respectively to the sensor response at the upper and lower stress levels during a cycle. It appears that the sensor reacts after 8200 cycles only, while the pipe weeping occurs after 14000 cycles. At that moment, the pipe shows 24% axial modulus loss, 5% hoop modulus loss, and the hoop strain reaches 0,50% (value similar to that measured during burst tests and close to that determined on test samples (0,45%)). Thus cycling does not affect the strain threshold for which the electric resistance increase of the sensor is noticed. An increase of the minimum electric resistance of 0,45 Ω is also noted after 14000 cycles: Nevertheless the

exploitation of this signal, even if possible, would be difficult in practice because of its low amplitude.

Fig.3: Composite pipe under dynamic internal pressure - Response of a carbon fibre sensor (0,36% nominal elongation at break) located in the hoop direction

Dynamic fatigue tests on pipes have shown that the use of the carbon fibre sensor makes it possible to monitor the damage state of the structure and to produce a preventing guard signal when such an industrial structure is submitted to a cyclic loading simulating real operating conditions over a short period of time.

MODELLING OF THE SENSORS ELECTRIC RESPONSE

The aim here is to define the necessary mathematical treatment allowing to link the electric resistance increase of the carbon tow to its strain, and thus, to change an electric signal into mechanical data related to the material. The design of a calculation code would then be possible, in order to follow in real time the damage of an instrumented part.

Modelling of the electric resistance increase due to carbon fibre elongation

The elongation of the carbon fibres induces an increase of their length, a decrease of their cross-section and thus an increase of their electric resistance, which can be calculated assuming that the carbon tow and the composite material experience the same longitudinal strain ϵ . Taking into account the Poisson's ratio ν effect of the carbon fibres, the electric resistance increase ΔR_e due to fibre elongation is then directly related to the applied strain ϵ and the initial electric resistance R_0 of the elongated carbon fibre portion (efficient length) according to equation (1). Nevertheless due to the low amplitude of these electric resistance differences, it is very difficult to implement a monitoring method based on fibre elongation on industrial parts.

$$\Delta R_e = R_0 \epsilon (1 + 2 \nu) \quad (1)$$

Modelling of the electric resistance increase due to carbon fibre fracture

It is possible to calculate the number of broken carbon fibres from the electric resistance increase of the carbon tow, considering that all the carbon fibres are arranged in parallel in the tow and have the same electric resistance [10]. The initial electric resistance R_0 of the carbon tow is then given by the ratio of the electric resistance R_F of one single fibre to the total

number of carbon fibres N (equation (2)). If n carbon fibres are broken, the increase of electric resistance ΔR_r due to fibre fracture is thus expressed by equation (3).

$$R_0 = \frac{R_F}{N} \quad (2)$$

$$\left(\frac{\Delta R_r}{R_0} \right)_n = \frac{(n/N)}{1 - (n/N)} \quad \text{i.e.} \quad n = \frac{\Delta R_r N}{R_0 + \Delta R_r} \quad (3)$$

Now it is well known that the mechanical resistance and ultimate elongation of a carbon fibre are directly related to the probability of defects existing along it. According to the weakest link theory, the fracture probability of a single filament corresponds to the fracture probability of the weakest link containing the most critical defect and is given by equation (4) for a fibre of length L , where σ_r is the ultimate strength, σ the applied stress and $\theta(\sigma)$ an empirical function (most of the time, Weibull or sigmoid functions are chosen to describe the carbon fibre fracture). This equation is also valid for strains, providing a substitution of σ into ε .

$$\Pr(\sigma_r < \sigma) = 1 - \exp(-\theta(\sigma) L) \quad (4)$$

Weibull model:

Some authors [11,12] have modelled the defect population, estimated from tensile tests on single filaments or dry carbon tow, thanks to Weibull functions assuming that:

- 1: From an electrical point of view, all the fibres are arranged in parallel in the carbon tow. The transverse electric contacts between different fibres are neglected: Each single filament is ideally electrically isolated from its neighbours by a resin layer.
- 2: The strains of the composite test sample and of the embedded carbon tow are equal. Effects due to differences in initial tension of the filaments are neglected.
- 3: The influences of the matrix and of the glass-resin host material on the fibre fracture are neglected; only one unique fracture per fibre is taken into account.

The fracture probability of the carbon fibres is then given by equation (5), where ε_r is the ultimate strain, N the total number of fibres and n the number of broken fibres for the applied strain ε . Writing equation (4) in term of strains, it is possible to express the function as follows (equation (6)).

$$P(\varepsilon_r < \varepsilon) = \frac{n}{N} = \frac{\Delta R}{R_0 + \Delta R} \quad (5)$$

$$\theta(\varepsilon) = -\frac{\ln(1 - P(\varepsilon_r < \varepsilon))}{L} = -\frac{1}{L} \ln \left[1 - \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0 + \Delta R} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

Now, the 3 parameters Weibull distribution being given by equation (7), a combination with (6) leads to the final relationship (8) between strain ε and electric resistance ΔR .

$$\theta(\varepsilon) = \left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_s}{\varepsilon_0} \right)^m \quad (7)$$

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 [\theta(\varepsilon)]^{1/m} + \varepsilon_s = \varepsilon_0 \left[-\frac{1}{L} \ln \left[1 - \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0 + \Delta R} \right) \right] \right]^{1/m} + \varepsilon_s \quad (8)$$

with ϵ_0 : scale (or width) parameter m : shape parameter (dimensionless exponent)
 ϵ_s : onset parameter (threshold strain for which the fracture probability still equals 0)

ϵ_s corresponds to the strain at which the first fracture of the carbon tow occurs. It is experimentally determined from an analysis of the amplitude of acoustic emission signals, assuming that carbon fibre failures induce signals of amplitudes higher than 95 dB, while signals of lower amplitudes come from matrix and interface cracking. The coefficients ϵ_0 and m are fitted on the basis of a mean square regression. The values of the coefficients of equation (8) are given on figure 4 for a carbon sensor of 0,6% nominal ultimate elongation under monoaxial tension.

Sigmoid model:

Other authors [13] have chosen sigmoid functions to model the fracture distribution during multifragmentation tests (tensile tests on impregnated fibres). In that case, the test coupons are made of one single carbon filament embedded in a ductile matrix. After the first fibre break, interfacial shearing stresses enable to load the fibre again: The carbon filament still keeps its reinforcement role. The final failure of the test sample thus occurs after successive fractures of the filament, which multiply until the mean length of the fragments reaches the critical length representative of the fibre/matrix system, for which the filament is no longer able to reinforce the matrix.

Assumptions 1 and 2 previously made for Weibull model are still valid here, but this new model now takes into account multiple fractures for a same fibre. Thus it suits better from a mechanical point of view. For this model, the fracture probability is expressed as a function of the number of fractures and no longer as a function of the number of broken fibres (many breaks per fibre are possible). Nevertheless, assuming that the number (a) of possible fractures is the same for each carbon fibre and that the fractures preferentially occur on the same fibre, the expression of fracture probability which is finally obtained is the same as previously (equation (5)) as shows equation (9).

$$P(\epsilon_r < \epsilon) = \frac{n_r}{N_{rt}} = \frac{a \cdot n}{a \cdot N} = \frac{n}{N} \quad (9)$$

with n_r : number of fractures n : number of broken fibres
 N_{rt} : total number of possible fractures N : total number of fibres
 a : number of fractures per fibre

As a consequence, equation (6) remaining unchanged, its combination with the expression (10) of the sigmoid function leads to the final relationship (11). A is an empirical coefficient. The other coefficients ϵ_0 , ϵ_s and m are determined as previously and are given on figure 4 in the case of a carbon sensor of 0,6% nominal ultimate elongation subjected to axial tension.

$$\theta(\epsilon) = A \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\epsilon - \epsilon_s}{\epsilon_0} \right)^m \right] \right\} \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_0 \left[-\ln \left(1 - \frac{\theta(\epsilon)}{A} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{m}} + \epsilon_s = \epsilon_0 \left[-\ln \left(1 - \frac{1}{LA} \ln \left[1 - \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0 + \Delta R} \right) \right] \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{m}} + \epsilon_s \quad (11)$$

Parameters	Weibull	Sigmoid
R_{o_mean} (Ω)	12,287	12,287
L (m)	0,16	0,16
ϵ_s (%)	0,65	0,65
m	3,51	3,94
ϵ_o (%)	0,185	6,088
A	-	34,5

Parameters of Weibull and sigmoid functions

Fig.4. Comparison of experimental/calculated results for tensile test on test coupons (carbon tow of 0,6% nominal elongation at break)

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF MODELS

Application to test coupons subjected to uniaxial monotonic tension

Figure 4 shows that there is a good correlation between the mean experimental data and the calculated Weibull curve for resistance increases going up to 17 Ω (corresponding to strains up to 0,87%). For higher resistance increases, the slope of the Weibull curve is higher than that of the experimental curve, because Weibull functions take into account only one fracture per carbon fibre, each fracture leading to an electric resistance increase. In a real life situation, the same carbon fibre may break many times, and successive fractures on the same fibres do not induce any significant electric resistance variation. The higher the number of broken fibres, the higher the probability of multiple fractures: This could explain the observed divergences between experimental and calculated curves at high strains. In return the beginning of the experimental curve is well fitted by the Weibull model, because the probability to obtain two fractures on the same fibre is very low at the tensile test beginning. This probability is also reduced by the load transfer effect between neighbouring fibres, which favours distinct fibre fractures rather than multiple fractures on the same fibre [14]

When the Weibull function starts to diverge from the experimental curve, the sigmoid function, which does not fit experimental data for lower strains, starts to fit them well. The model change occurs at an electric resistance increase of 16 Ω , that is to say according to equation (5), for 56% of broken carbon fibres. At that point the fracture probability of a fibre already broken once becomes higher than the probability to break a new intact carbon fibre. Thus the Weibull function can be associated to an electric resistance / strain behaviour law, where each carbon fibre is only broken once, and the sigmoid function to a behaviour law taking into account multiple fractures for a same carbon fibre (and this induces a slower increase of the electric resistance). Multiple carbon fibre fractures are confirmed by a visual inspection of the tow after tensile tests: an average of six major fractures are regularly spaced on the whole width of the carbon tow.

Application to pipes under increasing internal pressure

The aim is to determine the damage state of a pipe submitted to a given internal pressure and instrumented with a hoop carbon tow only (ultimate elongation 0,36 %). For this purpose one needs to calculate the pipe strain from the electric resistance increase due to the carbon fibre fractures, using the appropriate model. Then, the value of this strain is compared to the strain critical threshold corresponding to the first damage of the structure, previously determined by the user (finite element calculations carried out in design departments or experimental determination on prototypes). The value of the strain threshold is here given by the knee-point of the stress-strain curves (0,54 % ± 0,005) recorded during the initial characterisation of the composite structure. Moreover it is assumed that the electric resistance / strain curves of the carbon tows under biaxial loading can be modelled by the same kind of equations as those used under uniaxial tension. The critical strain of 0,54% being just above the fracture strain of the carbon tows used (0,51 % ± 0,007), it is necessary to use a Weibull function to model the electric resistance / strain curve. The coefficients of the Weibull for pipes, fitted on the basis of a mean square regression, are given on figure 5. It appears that the calculated curve fits well the experimental data up to 0,59% strain.

Fig.5: Comparison of experimental/calculated results for a pipe under internal pressure (carbon tow of 0,36% nominal elongation at break)

In short, from a simple measurement of the electric resistance, the user is able to determine whether the composite structure is damaged or not. For an electric resistance increase lower than 7,1 Ω , the calculated strain remains under the pipe first damage threshold: the structure is undamaged. On the other hand, if the electric resistance increase measured is higher than 7,1 Ω , that means that the structural integrity of the pipe has been lost.

CONCLUSIONS

This research program made it possible, in the first stage, to implement the resistive damage sensor developed on simple industrial parts: Composite pipes submitted to an internal pressure loading. For this purpose, it was necessary to choose a type of carbon fibre having characteristics adapted to the first damage critical strains of the structure to be monitored. In the second stage, a modelling of the resistive sensor electric response has allowed to design a calculation code aiming to determine in real time, if the damage threshold of the composite structure has been overgone or not. Thus a simple instrumented composite part being able to self-monitor its damage state has been successfully developed. This monitoring concept still

needs to be validated on more complex geometries and more complex loading modes.

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